

EFL EDUCATION AS A CATALYST FOR BULLYING: SOCIO-ECONOMIC DIVIDES, ACADEMIC PRESSURE, AND AI IN GREEK SCHOOLS

Michail St. Fountoulakis, Ph.D.

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DISCUSSION NOTE

Faculty at Hellenic Police Academy,
Hellenic Police Officers School &
National School of Public
Administration, Greece
Email: mihalis.fountoulakis@gmail.com

Abstract

This article explores the intersection between English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education and bullying in Greek schools. It examines how academic pressures, socio-economic divides, and the prominence of private tutoring contribute to a competitive and exclusionary classroom culture that fosters bullying. The psychological and social impacts of performance anxiety and peer rivalry are evaluated. The discussion also highlights potential interventions, including teacher training, curriculum modifications, and addressing the growing role of AI-driven tools in education.

Keywords: Education, Bullying Social impacts Interventions.

1. Introduction

Bullying in Greek public schools, particularly among students aged 6 to 15, is often driven by academic pressure and socio-economic inequalities (Sapouna, 2008). However, less attention has been given to the role of EFL education in exacerbating these issues. Bourou and Papageorgiou (2023) note that “English proficiency has become a high-stakes requirement, which, combined with socio-economic divides, creates intense stress for students” (p.391). This is particularly true when students are enrolled in private test-prep schools, amplifying disparities.

The dual schooling system in Greece—public education supplemented by private language instruction—intensifies these divides. Economic disparities between students attending private language schools and those who do not, alongside competition in EFL classrooms, foster environments conducive to bullying (Pateraki & Houndoumadi, 2001). This issue extends beyond Greece, with studies highlighting how competition in language learning can fuel bullying behaviors globally (O'Donnell & Schwab-Stone, 2017).

2. Background and Literature Review

2.1 Bullying in Greek Schools

Bullying in Greek schools is a well-documented issue, influenced by socio-economic inequalities and academic pressure (Sapouna, 2008; Bourou & Papageorgiou, 2023). However, earlier studies largely overlook the specific role of EFL education. According to Pateraki and Houndoumadi (2001), “Language certification exams place significant pressure on students, leading to performance anxiety and peer bullying” (p. 168). This phenomenon

mirrors findings in other regions, where competitive academic environments increase peer victimization (Smith et al., 2016).

2.2 EFL Education in Greece

English language instruction is central to the Greek education system, starting in primary school and intensifying in junior high. Students often prepare for high-stakes exams like those offered by Cambridge and Michigan (Bourou & Papageorgiou, 2023). The socio-economic divide between students who can afford private tutoring and those who cannot is significant (Fountoulakis, 2024). In wealthier areas like Agios Stefanos and Glyfada, students are more likely to have access to private tutoring, outperforming their peers from working-class areas like Egaleo and Evgenia, where fewer families can afford such services. Similar disparities exist in other European countries, where private tutoring often exacerbates academic inequalities and bullying (Bray & Lykins, 2012).

2.3 AI-Driven Tools and Bullying in EFL Education

The introduction of AI-driven tools into education has added a new layer to the socio-economic disparities in classrooms. While AI tools can enhance language proficiency, they can also heighten competition, particularly when access is uneven (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Wealthier students, with access to advanced AI learning platforms, tend to outperform their peers, which reinforces socio-economic divides and contributes to bullying behaviors. Fountoulakis (2024) notes, “AI technology, while beneficial for language learning, inadvertently intensifies competition by creating unequal access to learning resources” (p. 22). This phenomenon is echoed in international studies showing that unequal access to educational technology can foster feelings of inferiority and peer exclusion (Selwyn, 2016).

2.4 Performance Anxiety and Peer Competition

Performance anxiety is a key factor contributing to bullying, especially in competitive academic environments. This issue is particularly prominent in EFL classrooms, where public speaking and oral participation are essential to success (Bourou & Papageorgiou, 2023). Recent research emphasizes that high-stakes environments, such as language certification exams, amplify stress, leading to higher incidences of bullying and aggression (Juvonen & Graham, 2014). Pateraki and Houndoumadi (2001) highlight similar findings, noting that “peer competition and public performance comparisons in EFL classrooms are significant contributors to bullying” (p. 170).

2.5 Socio-Economic Disparities and Private Tutoring

A recurring theme in the literature is the socio-economic divide that characterizes EFL education. Students attending private test-prep schools, such as those in Agios Stefanos and Glyfada, consistently outperform their peers in language exams and show greater classroom confidence (Pateraki & Houndoumadi, 2001). In contrast, students from areas like Egaleo and Evgenia, where access to private tutoring is less prevalent, are more vulnerable to bullying and academic marginalization. Similar trends are reported globally, where private tutoring services widen academic gaps and increase bullying based on perceived academic inferiority (Bray & Kwo, 2014).

2.6 Social and Cultural Pressures to Learn English

The cultural expectation that English proficiency is essential for academic and professional success places additional pressure on students in Greece. Those who fail to meet these expectations are often ridiculed or ostracized, reinforcing bullying behaviors (Pateraki & Houndoumadi, 2001). Research by Ditchburn (2017)

confirms this broader trend, where social pressures around language learning contribute to exclusionary behaviors. Houndoumadi et al. (2003) similarly argue that “the pressure to succeed in language education is not just academic but also deeply cultural, contributing to peer victimization” (p. 173).

3. Discussion

3.1 Impact of Bullying on Academic Performance and Well-Being

3.1.1 Absenteeism and Avoidance

Bullying in EFL classrooms often leads to absenteeism, with students avoiding school to escape harassment. Sapouna (2008) emphasizes that victims of bullying in Greek schools “tend to exhibit higher levels of school avoidance, which ultimately impacts their academic performance” (p. 200). In language classes, where oral participation is crucial, this avoidance severely hampers progress (Bourou & Papageorgiou, 2023).

3.1.2 Psychological Toll and Emotional Impact

Bullying can have severe emotional and psychological effects, including anxiety, depression, and a lack of self-confidence (Juvonen & Graham, 2014). These issues are particularly damaging in subjects like EFL, where confidence in speaking is essential. According to Smith et al. (2016), “Bullying undermines a student's ability to engage, leading to diminished academic outcomes and emotional disengagement from the learning process” (p. 57).

3.1.3 Peer Isolation and Exclusion

The social isolation that results from bullying is detrimental to collaborative learning, a key element in language acquisition. Bourou and Papageorgiou (2023) note, “EFL classes require active peer interaction, and bullying severely disrupts these necessary social exchanges” (p. 395). Peer exclusion, particularly in group-based learning environments, further marginalizes students.

3.2 The Role of Private Test-Prep Schools in Exacerbating Bullying

3.2.1 Economic Inequality and Academic Superiority

Private test-prep schools contribute to a two-tiered system of education, reinforcing socio-economic divides. According to Bray and Lykins (2012), “Private tutoring exacerbates educational inequalities by creating an advantage for students who can afford extra lessons, fostering superiority and marginalization” (p. 93). This dynamic is evident in Greek schools, where students from wealthier families dominate EFL classrooms (Pateraki & Houndoumadi, 2001).

3.2.2 Competitive Classroom Environment

The competitive nature of EFL instruction, particularly when linked to certification exams, exacerbates bullying. Students who excel academically may assert their dominance over their less advantaged peers (Bourou & Papageorgiou, 2023). International research similarly indicates that competitive educational environments increase the risk of bullying (Juvonen & Graham, 2014).

3.2.3 Technological Disparities and AI Tools

AI tools are transforming EFL education, but the unequal access to these platforms contributes to bullying. Fountoulakis (2024) notes, “The integration of AI-driven platforms in EFL instruction offers students from wealthier backgrounds a distinct advantage, further isolating students from working-class areas like Egaleo and Evgenia who may lack access to such resources” (p. 24). This technological divide deepens socio-economic disparities and increases the likelihood of bullying in classrooms where these tools are used.

3.3 Addressing Bullying in EFL Classrooms

3.3.1 Teacher Training and Intervention

Effective teacher training programs are essential for addressing bullying in EFL classrooms. Teachers need the skills to recognize and intervene in cases of bullying, especially those related to academic performance and socio-economic disparities (Houndoumadi et al., 2003). International research suggests that teacher interventions in bullying scenarios can significantly reduce its incidence in schools (Olweus, 2013).

3.3.2 Curriculum Adjustments

Adapting the curriculum to promote collaboration over competition can foster a more inclusive environment. Group projects, peer tutoring, and alternative assessment methods can reduce performance pressures and encourage a more supportive classroom culture (Bourou & Papageorgiou, 2023).

4. Conclusion

The role of EFL education in triggering bullying in Greek schools is complex, driven by academic pressure, socio-economic inequalities, and competitive classroom environments. The reliance on private test-prep schools exacerbates these issues, creating hierarchies that fuel bullying. The psychological and academic impacts on students are profound, leading to absenteeism, disengagement, and emotional distress. Addressing these challenges requires systemic reforms to ensure more equitable access to quality EFL education and anti-bullying interventions that promote empathy and collaboration in the classroom.

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